

(III)

Following the formulation suggested by Rây and his co-workers in previous papers for metal-biguanide complexes, the structure of copper and nickel ethylenedibiguanide compounds is represented by the formula IV.

(IV)

X_2 , where Me = Cu or Ni;
X = any anion.

Dübsky and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have described only the corresponding insoluble copper and nickel ethylenedibiguanide sulphate. In the present paper a large number of other salts will be discussed. Attempts to prepare the free bases led to rather impure products. As could be expected, no indication of the formation of isomeric modifications was obtained in either case. The colour and the diamagnetic character of the nickel complex, however, definitely indicate its planar structure with *d-s-p*² hybrid bonds.

The same authors have stated that cobalt, unlike copper and nickel, does not combine with ethylenedibiguanide to form any co-ordination complex. A yellow precipitate obtained with ordinary cobalt salt solution was attributed by them to the presence of nickel as an impurity in the cobalt salt. This is, however, wrong and does not present the actual facts. For, we have succeeded in preparing cobaltous ethylenedibiguanide sulphate in the form of bright yellow, silky, crystalline precipitate from nickel-free cobalt salt solution. Cobaltous complexes are usually unstable and readily change into the cobaltic type. But the present compound was found to be quite stable and resembles the corresponding nickel complex in its general properties. No other salt, besides the sulphate, could, however, be prepared. The stability of the sulphate, therefore, appears to be due to its high degree of insolubility. On treatment with alkali it changes into a pale yellow product—the free complex base in a more or less impure state. On boiling with water it suffers oxidation forming a red solution of a cobaltic complex. Double decomposition of the sulphate with soluble barium salts led to the formation of oxidised products like hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic-ethylenedibiguanide salts.

Though the formation of complex cobaltous biguanide base has been referred to in a previous paper (Rây and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 4), its preparation in a pure state, as well as that of the corresponding sulphate, along with their properties remain to be described here. They resemble the corresponding nickel compounds in colour; the sulphate is,

however, decomposed readily by warm water with separation of green cobaltous hydroxide. Even water at room temperature leads to gradual decomposition. This can be represented as a case of hydrolysis :

Formation of the green hydroxide by the hydrolysis of a fourfold cobaltous complex suggests that the green modification of cobaltous hydroxide should be preferably represented as diaquo-dihydroxo-cobalt with no free ionic hydroxyl groups.

The magnetic moment of all the cobaltous complexes described above are considerably lower than that of the simple cobaltous salts or of the associated cobaltous complexes. They are to be regarded, therefore, as penetration complexes having planar configuration with *d-s-p*² hybrid bonds. The magnetic measurements will be described in a separate paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper Ethylenedibiguanidinium Salts

Sulphate.—An intimate mixture of equimolecular quantities of ethylenediamine hydrochloride (8 g.) and dicyandiamide (5 g.) was fused between 140°-150°. The product was dissolved in water, filtered and the solution concentrated to eliminate the unreacted dicyandiamide which separated out. The filtrate was then precipitated with a solution of copper sulphate. The rose-red crystals of copper ethylenedibiguanide sulphate were first washed thoroughly with cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. {Found: N, 32'40; SO₄, 22'32; Cu, 14'71. [CuEn(BigH⁺)₂]SO₄·1½H₂O requires N, 32'43; SO₄, 22'24; Cu, 14'73 per cent}. En(BigH)₂=a molecule of ethylenedibiguanide, C₄N₁₀H₁₄.

The substance is almost insoluble in water, unaffected by dilute acids. Strong acids lead to its decomposition with formation of simple copper salts. Alkalis liberate the free complex base. This compound corresponds to that described by Důbský and co-workers as well as by Dittler (*loc. cit.*).

Chloride.—An aqueous suspension of the crude copper ethylenedibiguanidinium hydroxide, obtained by digesting the complex sulphate with caustic soda solution, was treated with ammonium chloride. On cooling the red solution, rose-red needle-shaped crystals of the chloride separated. These were purified by recrystallisation from hot water. The product was washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 36'10; Cl, 18'30; Cu, 16'45. Cu[En(BigH⁺)₂]Cl₂·1½H₂O requires N, 36'03; Cl, 18'25; Cu, 16'36 per cent}.

Equivalent conductivity at 32°.

<i>v</i> (litres)	...	64	128	256	512	1024
Λ_v	...	114'9	119'4	123'4	126'9	131'1

$\Lambda_{\infty}(\text{mean}) = 134'6$, from Walden's formula, $\Lambda_{\infty} = \Lambda_e (1 + n_1 n_2 \cdot 0'692 \cdot v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$, where n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

Hence the equivalent mobility of the complex [CuEn(BigH⁺)₂] ion is equal to 134'6-85'0 = 49'6, 85'0 being the mobility of Cl-ion at 32°. For copper biguanidinium chloride, Λ_{∞} was found to be 144'6 at 35° by Rây and Bagchi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 617); from which the equivalent conductivity for [Cu(BigH⁺)₂] ion is 144'6-89'2 = 55'4 at 35°, 89'2 being the mobility of Cl-ion at that temperature. On making corrections for the temperature difference it appears that the mobility of copper ethylenedibiguanidinium ion is only slightly lower than that of copper biguanidinium ion, which is to be expected.

Bromide was prepared by using ammonium bromide in the same way as the chloride. The product was purified by thrice recrystallisation from water. It forms silky, rose-red crystals, comparatively less soluble than the chloride. {Found: Br, 33'40; Cu, 13'25. $[\text{CuEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot \text{Br}_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Br, 33'47; Cu, 13'31 per cent}.

Iodide was prepared by using ammonium iodide in the same way as the chloride or bromide. The deep purple solution on cooling deposited pink coloured needles of the iodide. These were recrystallised twice from water and dried in air. The crystals were moderately soluble in alcohol. {Found: I, 44'26; Cu, 11'18. $[\text{CuEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot \text{I}_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I, 44'43; Cu, 11'13 per cent}.

Thiosulphate.—The complex thiosulphate was obtained as a voluminous rose-red precipitate on mixing a solution of the complex chloride with that of sodium thiosulphate. {Found: S, 14'30; Cu, 14'28. $[\text{CuEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S, 14'30; Cu, 14'20 per cent}.

Thiocyanate was obtained as a deep pink coloured crystalline precipitate by adding a concentrated solution of potassium thiocyanate to that of the complex chloride. The substance is moderately soluble in alcohol and water. {Found: S, 14'86; Cu, 14'80. $[\text{CuEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot (\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S, 14'76; Cu, 14'67 per cent}.

Nitrate was prepared by the action of ammonium nitrate on the aqueous suspension of the complex base. From the pink solution, on cooling, silky rose-red needles of the nitrate separated out. These were purified by recrystallisation from hot water. {Found: Cu, 14'35; NO_2 , 28'18. $[\text{CuEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot (\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 14'40; NO_2 , 28'08 per cent}.

Nitrite was obtained by adding a strong solution of sodium nitrite to that of the complex chloride in the cold. It forms pink coloured crystals, soluble in water. {Found: Cu, 15'56; NO_2 (gas volumetrically as N_2), 22'50. $[\text{CuEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot (\text{NO})_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 15'52; NO_2 , 22'47 per cent}.

Copper Ethylenedibiguanidine.—When a solution of the pure complex chloride was treated with dilute ammonia, a light rose-red precipitate of the base was obtained. This was washed with ice-cold water and dried in air, free from CO_2 . {Found: N, 45'80; Cu, 20'36. $[\text{CuEn}(\text{Big})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 45'50; Cu, 20'68 per cent}.

Use of caustic alkali solution in place of ammonia leads to partial decomposition and hence a more impure product. It seems ethylenedibiguanide is affected by strong alkalis.

Nickel Ethylenedibiguanidinium Salts

Sulphate was prepared exactly in the same way as the corresponding complex sulphate of copper. It forms orange-yellow crystals, sparingly soluble in water. {Found: N, 33'90; Ni, 14'09; SO_4 , 23'10. $[\text{NiEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 33'52; Ni, 14'06; SO_4 , 23'0 per cent}. (*cf.* also Dübsky and co-workers, *loc. cit.*).

Chloride.—The solution, obtained by extracting the fused mixture of ethylenediamine hydrochloride and dicyandiamide (see preparation of copper ethylenedibiguanidinium sulphate) after the removal of the unreacted dicyandiamide, was treated with a solution of nickel chloride and heated on the water-bath. The resulting orange-yellow solution, on cooling, deposited silky, orange-coloured needles of the complex chloride. This was recrystallised twice from water, washed and dried as usual. It decomposes on warming with dilute acids. {Found: N, 36'92; Ni, 15'35; Cl, 18'50. $[\text{NiEn}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 36'31; Ni, 15'31; Cl, 18'49 per cent}. Magnetic susceptibility: $\chi_m = 0.4436 \times 10^{-6}$.

Equivalent conductivity at 34°

v (litres)	...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
$\Lambda_s =$	...	104	116	124	130	133	138

$\lambda \infty = 138.5$ (from Walden's formula).

Hence the equivalent mobility of $[\text{Ni En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]$ at $34^\circ = 138.5 - 87.78 = 50.72$, 87.78 being the mobility of Cl^- ion at 34° . The corresponding value for $[\text{Ni}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]$, calculated from Rây and Purakayastha's results (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 219) = 54.6 .

Bromide was obtained in the form of silky, orange needles by treating a strong solution of the complex chloride with that of potassium bromide. The product was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. {Found: Ni, 12.02; Br, 32.80. $[\text{Ni En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 11.97; Br, 32.59 per cent.}

Iodide was prepared like the bromide from the complex chloride and potassium iodide. The orange-yellow, needle-shaped crystals were purified by recrystallisation from water. {Found: Ni, 10.42; I, 45.37. $[\text{Ni En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \text{I}_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.36; I, 44.82 per cent.}

Thiosulphate.—Orange-yellow precipitate of the thiosulphate was at once obtained by adding a solution of sodium thiosulphate to that of the complex chloride. The substance is very sparingly soluble in water. {Found: S_2O_3 , 50.75; Ni, 13.35. $[\text{Ni En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S_2O_3 , 50.57; Ni, 13.26 per cent.}

Thiocyanate.—When a concentrated solution of potassium thiocyanate was added to that of the complex chloride and cooled, silky orange-coloured crystals of the complex thiocyanate separated out. These were purified by recrystallisation. The product is moderately soluble in alcohol. {Found: S, 14.89; Ni, 13.66. $[\text{Ni En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] (\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S, 14.93; Ni, 13.70 per cent.}

Nitrate was obtained as a buff-coloured curdy precipitate from a solution of potassium nitrate and that of the complex chloride. The product was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. {Found: Ni, 13.48; NO_3 , 28.80. $[\text{Ni En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] (\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 13.44; NO_3 , 28.39 per cent.}

Nitrite.—The light orange coloured curdy precipitate of the nitrite was obtained by adding a concentrated solution of sodium nitrite to that of the complex chloride. This was then recrystallised from water. {Found: N(total), 41.22; Ni, 14.59. $[\text{Ni En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] (\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N(total), 41.51; Ni, 14.50 per cent.}

When a solution of the complex chloride was treated with either dilute NaOH or ammonia, a silky, brownish orange precipitate of the complex base was obtained. This, on analysis, was found to contain proportionately more nitrogen and less nickel than the theoretically required value for nickel ethylenedibiguanidine or its hydroxide. All attempts to prepare a pure base, by altering the conditions of preparation, were unsuccessful (*cf.* preparation of the complex copper base).

Cobaltous Complexes

Cobaltous Ethylenedibiguanidinium Sulphate.—A solution of ethylenedibiguanide sulphate (2 mol.) in dilute ammonia was added, drop by drop, with constant stirring to that of nickel-free

$\text{CoCl}_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mol.) in a little water. A greenish yellow silky precipitate separated at once. This turned yellow on warming on the water-bath. It was washed by decantation with cold water and then thoroughly on the filter until free from chloride and finally with alcohol. The product was dried over CaCl_2 .

The compound is very sparingly soluble in water and is decomposed by dilute mineral acids, though comparatively stable towards dilute acetic acid. On treatment with dilute NaOH solution it changes into the corresponding light yellow complex base. On digestion with ammonia it undergoes gradual oxidation with the formation of cobaltic complexes giving a red solution. When treated with a solution of barium chloride an alkaline violet-coloured solution is produced, suggesting the formation of a hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic complex. A similar decomposition occurs with boiling water. This is supported by the fact that the violet solution on treatment with sodium thiosulphate gives a green precipitate on acidification (*cf.* Ray and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 1). {Found: N, 32'96; Co, 13'75; SO_4 , 22'32. $[\text{Co En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 32'79; Co, 13'80; SO_4 , 22'47 per cent}. It loses one molecule of water of hydration at 80° , but regains the same on subsequent exposure to the atmosphere.

Cobaltous Ethylenedibiguanidinium Base.—When the complex sulphate was treated with very dilute caustic soda solution in the cold, a light yellow precipitate of the free anhydro base was obtained in a rather impure state. This was washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The product was dried in vacuum over calcium chloride and lime. {Found: N, 47'8; Co, 21'10. $[\text{Co En}(\text{Big})_2]$ requires N, 49'1; Co, 20'7 per cent}.

On shaking with dilute ammonia it undergoes oxidation to the cobaltic state giving a red solution. A similar oxidation occurs on boiling with water with the formation of cobaltous and cobaltic hydroxides.

Cobaltous biguanidinium sulphate was obtained as a greenish yellow silky precipitate by adding a cold solution of the calculated quantity (2 mols.) of simple biguanide sulphate in dilute ammonia to that of nickel-free $\text{CoCl}_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mol.). A solution of ammonium sulphate was then added to the mixture and the latter agitated for sometime in the cold. The precipitate was washed at first with ice-cold water containing a little ammonium sulphate, then with water alone and finally with cold alcohol. It was dried in vacuum over calcium chloride. Air should be excluded during washing and drying. {Found: N, 32'20; Co, 13'84; SO_4 , 22'46; H_2O (by loss at 105° in a current of nitrogen), 16'40. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 32'63; Co, 13'75; SO_4 , 22'38; H_2O , 16'78 per cent}.

The anhydrous product is a pale dull yellow powder and gave on analysis, Co, 16'79%. (Calc. Co, 16'49%). On exposure to air at room temperature the dried product absorbed water to reform the original hydrated substance with $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The substance is decomposed by warm water as already described (*vide supra*). In presence of ammonium sulphate solution it suffers slight oxidation forming a red solution of a cobaltic complex. When heated in air it forms an oxidised product with reddish brown colour.

Cobaltous Biguanidine and its Hydroxide.—The base was precipitated in the form of small silky yellow flakes when a solution of biguanide sulphate (2 mols.) in excess of caustic soda was added to that of nickel-free $\text{CoCl}_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mol.). The precipitate was washed first

with ice-cold water, containing a few drops of ammonia. This was then filtered and washed on the filter successively with cold water, aqueous alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. The filtration and washing were carried out in a current of hydrogen gas in Kapsenberg's automatic filtration apparatus. The product was dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 . In the dry state it is fairly stable and keeps pure for a long time. When moist, it undergoes slow oxidation in air with formation of red cobaltic trisbiguanidinium hydroxide and separation of cobaltic oxide.

On boiling with water it changes slowly to give a violet solution of hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanide complex, as it gives a green precipitate with sodium thiosulphate solution, when acidified. {Found : N, 48'10; Co, 20'60; H_2O (by loss at 70°), 12'26. $[Co(BigH^+)_2](OH)_2$ requires N, 47'50; Co, 20'45; H_2O , 12'21 per cent.}

The hydroxylic water is lost at 70° forming the anhydro-base. On analysis it gave: N, 52'15. $[Co(Big)_2]$ requires N, 54'06%. This indicates slight decomposition.

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